

ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE THROUGH MEASURED CHANGE MANAGEMENT: FOCUS ON THE TELECOMMUNICATION INDUSTRY

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Abstract: The study looked at organizational performance through measured change management with a focus on the telecommunication industry in Delta State. For the study, a cross-sectional survey research design approach was used. The approach of stratified random sampling was utilised in the investigation. A structured questionnaire was employed in the study as the data-gathering tool. A test-retest methodology was used to determine the instrument's dependability. Multiple regression analysis, correlation, and descriptive statistics were applied. Results indicated that the change management process accounted for 70% of organisational performance changes. The following was found; that preparing for change ($\beta = 0.183$, $P < 0.05$) and creating a vision for change ($\beta = 0.084$, $P < 0.05$), significantly improve organisational performance in telecommunication firms in Warri. Among other things, the study suggested that establishing the framework, procedures, and systems necessary to steer and oversee a business in a way that increases long-term shareholder value by holding management accountable and boosting organisational performance is known as creating a vision for change. It offers the framework for establishing the organization's goals, as well as the means of accomplishing them and keeping track of performance also the concluded organizations should employ the service of internal change managers to work together with such experts employed externally to facilitate growth in performance and smooth change implementation. Managers are advised to anticipate change, especially in the telecommunication industry where changes occur every second. The study recommended that change is a crucial component of success If it is purposefully established, properly implemented, and adapted, change in an organization's strategy can affect how it functions, affecting everything from the organizational structure to employees' everyday activities.

Keywords: Change management, create a vision, implementation of change, telecommunications industry, and organizational performance

Introduction

The term 'change management' refers to the planned, managed, or systematic implementation of changes (Burns, 2018). The rate of change is so rapid, and the degree of obsolescence for organisations that resist change is so

great that many individuals are forced to choose between embracing change and perishing. Due to technological, economic, political, and social upheavals, the business climate of the twenty-first century is characterised by rapid change (Oluwaleke, Akhimie, Abdulraseed & Olanrewaju, 2023). Consequently, managing change includes controlling its human impact. The term 'change management' refers to the planned, managed, or systematic implementation of changes (Burns, 2018). The rate of change is so rapid, and the degree of obsolescence for organisations that resist change is so great that many individuals are forced to choose between embracing change and perishing. Due to technological, economic, political, and social upheavals, the business climate of the twenty-first century is characterized by rapid change (Ubi, Ojie & Akaa, 2020). Resistance management is essential to effectively embrace new processes and systems in an ongoing organisation, which is the primary objective of this transformation. Consequently, managing change includes controlling its human impact.

In the past fifty years, more and more businesses have grown quickly, which means that change management skills are needed to keep up with the speed of change. This is because of tough competition, new technologies that make business and operating models more flexible, and the progress of economies around the world (Agbo, 2018); Aninkan, 2018). Hence, "Change" is now impossible to avoid. For some reason, it seems to have become an inevitable part of doing business. It can't be stopped from happening (Ekechi & Umar, 2020). But companies should be ready to deal with change so that their success keeps getting better (Ike & Azeez, 2020; Lovely, Onyiyechukwu & Joseph, 2020). Ofuoku and Ogisi (2020) say that organisations that don't get ready for change management will have a limited future. Since change is a natural part of life, people who are too focused on the present or their memories of the past may put their future at risk.

This is because the business world is becoming less predictable. Big names in Nigeria's phone industry right now are MTN, Airtel, Globacom, and the new companies 9Mobile and Visafone (Thomas, 2014; Kimhi & Oliel, 2019). As the business world becomes less stable, it's clear that change management is needed to fix poor performance, adapt to new changes in the external environment, maintain a competitive edge (in terms of lower costs and higher quality), and ensure clear progress (Cross, 2019). Usually, powerful change comes from two main places: the inside and the outside. Improvements in technology or pressure from outside the group, such as the government or business rivals, are the first two. The second source comes from people, such as donors, managers, and workers. Regardless of the two sources, management is always faced with problems about how to handle change that is either inevitable or necessary. They aren't sure if they should change their organisational change goals or strategies to make the needed changes, or if they should just keep the same technology, HR, organisational structure, or business environment (Daniel, Okafor & Emerole, 2019).

MTN, Airtel, Globacom, and, more recently, 9 Mobile and Visafone are the big players in the Nigerian mobile phone market right now. The last two have been in the country for less than five years. Businesses have to deal with change because the business world is becoming more unstable. This could be done to fix any or all of these problems: bad performance, adapting to changes caused by outside pressures, getting or keeping a competitive edge (through lower prices and higher quality), and clear innovation (Egbosionu, 2020). There are two main places where organisational change comes from. The outside source and the inside source, external sources could be better technology, pressure from outside groups like the government or competitors in the same business, or changes in the organisation itself (Ekechi & Umar, 2020). People inside the company, like shareholders, management, or workers, could be the source of change. Anyone can see that things are changing, and when they do, management always has to figure out what to do about it.

The Problem

The research problem statement serves as the foundation for any research study, guiding the investigation and framing the issues to be addressed. In the context of the effect of change management processes on the organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms in Delta State, Nigeria, a potential research problem statement could be as follows:

The reason many telecom companies have gone out of business is that the industry's change management isn't working well. The rate of powerless endurance shows that there isn't a solid framework for how to carry out and manage hierarchical change. Again, this shows that there is a lot to learn about managing change. This investigation was started because of small changes in the telecommunications industry. Its goal is to show the hidden truths about how new ideas affect performance. If change isn't handled well, it could hurt the organization's performance, which could lead to the closing of the business, the loss of valuable employees, or the inability to meet the goals of investors. Customers could also become unhappy, which would mean they would likely switch to a close competitor, which would also hurt the overall performance of the business.

The number of enterprises in the industry in 2001, when it was deregulated, and the few remaining today is puzzling, the conclusion is that many of these enterprises that went under because they failed to manage the industry transformation that swept them away. The lack of a suitable framework for organisational change is shown in the low survival rate. Thus, change management requires extensive study. Using subtle developments in the telecommunications business, this study reveals how technological change is altering it. Change that is poorly managed can hurt performance, leading to the closure of the company, the loss of valued employees, the failure to meet shareholder financial goals, and customer dissatisfaction that could lead to them switching to competitors.

The telecommunication industry in Delta State, Nigeria, is undergoing rapid transformations driven by technological advancements, market dynamics, and regulatory changes. As telecommunication firms navigate these challenges, the impact of change management processes on organizational performance becomes a critical area of investigation. However, a gap exists in understanding the specific nuances of change management within the local context and its direct influence on the performance metrics of selected telecommunication firms in Delta State. Thus, investigating how change management processes affect the organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria is now the main focus of this study.

Study Objectives

- To examine the impact of preparation for change on the organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms under study.
- To ascertain the impact of creating a vision for change on the organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms under study.

Research Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant relationship between preparing for change and organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms under study.

There is no significant relationship between creating a vision for change and organizational performance of selected telecommunication firms under study.

Literature Foundations

Change Management

The term "change management" is broad and encompasses any method that aids a business in managing change, whether it be gradual or abrupt. Change management has grown in importance in today's world of increasing globalization and competition (Ufua, Osabohien, Imhonopi, Olujobi & Ogbari, 2020). Managers described the current business environment and market needs as chaotic, uncertain, disruptive, ever-changing, and complex. Complexity, connection, interconnectedness, and speed have significantly expanded over the past 20 or 30 years, producing a fundamentally new environment that necessitates the use of cutting-edge change management techniques (Ugwu, Osisioma, Onwuzuligbo and Nnaji-ihedinmah, 2020). Change management (CM) is the study of how individuals survive in organizations that are changing as well as the theory and practice of reshaping companies to adapt and prosper in a dynamic environment. An organization's direction, structure, and capabilities must be updated consistently to meet the constantly changing needs of both internal and external consumers, according to Moran and Brightman (2018). According to Zhang, Kuchinke, Woud, Velten and Margraf, (2018), change management is a group of core tools or frameworks made to keep any change initiative under control. The goal is frequently to lessen the effects and disruptions of the transition. An organization's direction, structure, and capabilities must constantly be reinvented to meet the changing expectations of internal and external clients as well as the environment (Onyema & Onuoha, 2020).

Change Management Process

The change management process is a systematic approach to transitioning individuals, teams, and organizations from their current state to a desired future state. It involves a set of processes, tools, and techniques designed to effectively plan, implement, and manage change within an organization (Daniel, Okafor & Emerole, 2019). Here is a general overview of the change management process:

Prepare for Change: Identify the need for change by determining the reasons and objectives behind the proposed change. This may be driven by internal factors such as performance improvement or external factors such as market shifts, by assessing the organization's readiness for change by evaluating the organization's capacity, culture, and the level of support from leadership and employees (Egbosionu, 2020). By identifying and analyzing stakeholders: Understand who will be affected by the change and how. This includes employees, customers, suppliers, and other relevant parties. Communicate the need for change, involve key stakeholders in the decision-making process, and address concerns to gain their support (Ekechi & Umar, 2020).

Create a Vision for Change: Develop a comprehensive plan by outlining the scope, objectives, timelines, and resources required for the change initiative. Identifying risks by anticipating potential challenges developing strategies to mitigate risks and establishing measurable metrics to assess the success of the change (Etikan & Bala, 2017). Also, clearly articulate the reasons for the change, its benefits, and how it will be implemented, by ensuring that employees have the necessary knowledge and skills to adapt to the changes. Training programs may include workshops, seminars, and online resources (Fadila & Umar, 2021).

Organizational Performance

Shariff, Nasir, Ramli and Zahari, (2020) noted that organizational performance is positively impacted by the presence of change management practices, change management tends to create a significant contribution to organizational competencies, and in turn, becomes a great advance for further enhancing innovativeness. Performance may be measured using different matrices such as revenue, profitability, customer count, staff counts, market segment occupancy, and even sales volume. Irrespective of the matrix being used, several factors influence the level of performan

Conceptual Model of the Study

The conceptual model of the study depicts the independent and dependent variables of the study in figure 2.1 below;

Preparing for Change and Organization Performance

Change is an inevitable and essential aspect of organizational life in today's dynamic and competitive business environment (Abdullah, 2019). Organizations are constantly faced with the need to adapt to external and internal forces that require them to evolve and transform to remain relevant and successful (Abdullahi, Shehu, Usman, & Gumawa, 2020). The ability of an organization to effectively prepare for and manage change plays a crucial role in determining its overall performance and long-term success. The process of preparing for change involves a strategic and proactive approach to anticipating, initiating, and implementing changes within an organization. This includes conducting thorough assessments of current structures, systems, and processes, identifying the need for change, setting clear objectives and goals, engaging stakeholders, developing a change management plan, and implementing strategies to facilitate a smooth transition (Agama, Sylvanus & Kenneth, 2023). The impact of effective preparation for change on organizational performance is significant and multifaceted. By preparing for change, organizations can enhance their agility, flexibility, and responsiveness to market dynamics and emerging trends (Agbo, 2018). This enables them to stay ahead of the competition, capitalize on opportunities, and mitigate potential risks and disruptions. Moreover, a well-prepared organization is better positioned to minimize resistance to change, foster a positive organizational culture, and boost employee morale and engagement (Aninkan, 2018). This, in turn, can lead to higher levels of productivity, innovation, and overall performance across the organization (Atmowardoyo, 2018). In this context, the relationship between preparing for change and organizational performance is clear: organizations that invest in proactive and strategic change management processes are more likely to achieve sustained growth, profitability, and competitive advantage in the long run (Awiti, Imbambi, Mande & Machuki, 2020). Therefore, organizations must prioritize the readiness and readiness for change as a key driver of success in today's dynamic business landscape.

Creating a Vision for Change and Organization Performance

Creating a vision for change is a fundamental aspect of organizational development and growth. Organizations that successfully establish a clear and compelling vision for change can significantly enhance their performance and unlock new opportunities for success (Bansal & Gupta, 2019). A well-defined vision serves as a guiding beacon, aligning the efforts of employees towards a common goal and motivating them to work collaboratively towards achieving it (Bengat, Odenyo & Rotich, 2018). The effect of creating a vision for change on organizational performance is multifaceted and can result in various positive outcomes. One of the primary impacts of a vision for change on organizational performance is increased employee engagement and motivation (Bennis & Thomas, 2019). When employees understand and resonate with the vision of the organization, they are more likely to feel connected to their work and be inspired to contribute their best efforts. This heightened sense of purpose and direction can lead to improved productivity, creativity, and overall job satisfaction among employees. Furthermore, a clear vision for change can foster a culture of innovation and adaptability within the organization (Bersenaite, Saparnis & Saparniene, 2019). By outlining specific goals and objectives for the future, organizations can encourage employees to think creatively, experiment with new ideas, and adapt to changing market conditions (Caldwell, Chatman, Reilly, Ormiston & Lapiz, 2018). This proactive approach to change management enables organizations to stay ahead of the curve, seize growth opportunities, and remain competitive in a rapidly evolving business landscape. Moreover, a well-defined vision for change can enhance organizational alignment and cohesiveness. When all members of the organization are aligned around a common vision, silos are broken down, communication is improved, and collaboration becomes more effective (Christoffels, 2019). This alignment enables departments to work cohesively towards shared goals, leading to improved coordination, efficiency, and synergy across the organization. In addition, a compelling vision for change can attract top talent to the organization and retain high-performing employees. When potential hires and existing employees see a clear direction and purpose in the organization's vision, they are more likely to be drawn to the organization and remain committed to its success. This can result in a more skilled and engaged workforce, better equipped to drive organizational performance and achieve strategic objectives (Chukwuemeka, 2020).

Theoretical Review

Burke- Litwin Model of Organizational Change

The study was anchored on the Burke-Litwin model of organisational change, also known as the Causal Model of Organisational Change and Performance, which suggests that both internal and external factors should be linked to performance (Udeme& Umar, 2021). The theoretical model was created by Burke and Litwin in 1989. It gives us a good way to look at parts of the organisation and surroundings that are necessary for a change to work. This shows even more how the parts or characteristics are connected in a casual way to cause a difference in performance. The Burke-Litwin model shows how different measurements work together to make a change. In addition, it shows how outside factors affect the different parts of the organisation. This theory is very important because it gives us a way to plan and carry out organisational analysis and change management that clearly shows a cause-and-effect connection (Udeme & Umar, 2021). This model by Burke and Litwin shows how the outside environment, the organization's strategy and mission, its culture, its structure, the practices of management, its systems, the climate in the work units, people's jobs and skills, their needs and values, and their motivation are all likely to affect their performance as well as the performance of the organisation as a whole. However, the model had some problems when it came to managing change plans so that an organisation could do its job well. Some people don't like this model because they think it oversimplifies the different factors of change, which leads to the creation of sub-factors that make the model more complicated.

Empirical Review

In 2023, Agama, Sylvanus, and Kenneth investigated how organisational change affected the success of some construction companies. The people living their work for and are executives at five Nigerian building companies: RCC Building Company, Abacus Building Services, Dumez Nigeria Plc, and Enerco Nigeria Limited. The companies were picked because they were on the list made by the Federation of the Construction Industry (FOCI). Some of the criteria were size, number of current projects, geographic spread, and service portfolio. Twelve hundred and four people worked on the chosen construction site (1204), and the workers were first put into groups using the stratification method. A group of 300 people who answered the survey was chosen by Taro Yamane. These people were then statistically tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The study found a strong connection between not wanting to change and poor performance; important factors for managing change will have an impact on performance; and putting changes into action will have an impact on the performance of certain building firms. So, it was suggested that businesses find the best change model for their projects and then make changes to fit the situation. Companies should get information from more than one source, especially when looking for skill gaps, and workers should pay attention to training programmes set up by management.

Oluwaleke, Akhimie, Abdulraseed and Olanrewaju (2023) examined change management in the FMCG industry using selected firms in Lagos State with specific goals to investigate how much employee involvement, employee training, resources, and leadership affect change management in Lagos. The study adopted a descriptive research design, and the study population consists of all the managerial staff of the 25 most rated companies in the FMCG industry in Lagos. The sample size was 100 respondents. The online survey was used, and the data collected were analyzed using factor analysis. The empirical results indicate that all selected key factors contribute towards achieving effective change management as hypothesized. The results of this work may benefit enterprise managers planning, executing, and assessing change processes, as proper considerations of the factors discussed throughout this work may increase the chances of the change process success, resulting in a better performing and competitive enterprise.

Tools and Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Its purpose was to establish relationships between and among independent variables of study and organizational performance. The population of this study is limited to members of staff of selected telecommunication firms in Warri Delta State Nigeria, but targeting MTN, GLO and Airtel offices in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria from 2023 to 2024. The population used for this work comprises the employees, supervisors, and top managers of MTN, GLO and Airtel offices in Asaba, Delta State. Hence, the staff of MTN, GLO and Airtel offices in Asaba, Delta State would serve as our respondents and the population of the study. The breakdown of the population is MTN(30), Glo(28) and Airtel(17) medium and upper-level categories of management staff including contract carders.

Due to the size, the entire population was used as the sample size while construct validity referred to the degree to which a construct's operationalization did measure what the theory said it did. Quantitative data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics using SPSS version 23 and presented through percentages, means, standard deviations and frequencies. The data was split down into different aspects of the change management process on organizational performance.

Results and Discussion

Presentation of Data

Analysis from the Field Survey

Pattern focused	Number administered	Number returned	Unused copies	Number used	Response rate
Employees	75	70	5	70	93.33

Source: Distributed Questionnaire

70 of the 75 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed were returned, five were incomplete, and 70 were functional. Consequently, the study presented in this chapter was predicated on the 93.3% response rate acceptable sample size.

Table 4.2: Analysis of Respondents Profile

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender:		
	Male	25	36
	Female	45	64
	Total	70	100
2	Age Range:		
	Below 30 years	10	14.2
	31-40 years	40	57
	41years and above	20	28
	Total	70	100
3	Marital Status:		
	Single	25	40
	Married	45	60
	Total	70	100
4	Educational Qualification		
	WAEC/OND/NCE	-	-
	HND/B. Sc	53	76
	Masters/MBA	17	24
	Total	70	100
5	Level of Management		
	Lower	12	17
	Middle	40	57
	Top	18	26
	Total	70	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 exhibited the background characteristics of the various respondents. It indicated on the gender composition of the respondents representing 36% of the sample were males while 64% were females. According to the respondents' age brackets, 15% of the respondents were under the age of 30, 57% were between the ages of 31 and 40, and 28% were over the age of 41. The marital mix of the respondents revealed that 40% of the sample respondents were single, while 60% of the others were married. According to the respondents' educational backgrounds 76 percent had an HND/B.Sc, and 17 percent had a master's degree. On the level of management of staff, it was indicated that 17% of the respondents have lower management in the telecommunication industry. 57% of the respondents are middle level in the management . And lastly 34% of the respondents have above 11years working experience in the banking industry.

Analysis of Other Research Data

The analysis of the other research data and the testing of the earlier postulated hypotheses in previous chapter was done here to arrive at a conclusion and generalization.

Table 3 Inter-Correlations and Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables

S/N	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	M	SD
1.	Prepare for change (PC)						24.568	.6890
2.	Create a vision for change (CVC)	.088					24.473	.8188
55.	Organizational performance	.585**	.361**	.036	.434**	.691**	24.500	.9580

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4. The guideline for Pearson correlation coefficients

S/N	Coefficient value	Strength of association
1	0.1 < r < 0.3	Small correlation
2	0.3 < r < 0.5	Medium/moderate correlation
3	r > 0.5	Large/strong correlation

Source: Based on Cohen (2024)

Table 3 displayed the descriptive statistics and intercorrelations for the study variables. Prepare for change is a highly good indicator of organizational performance, as evidenced by the positive correlation coefficient (0.585) that was found between preparing for change and organisational performance. The moderately positive correlation coefficient (0.361) between create a vision for change and organizational performance suggests that preparing for change is an excellent indicator of organizational performance.

The small positive correlation coefficient (0.036) between implementing change and organisational performance indicates that implementing change is highly effective in ensuring organizational performance. Embed and solidify is a highly good indicator of change management, as evidenced by the positive correlation coefficient (0.434) that was found between Embed and solidify and organisational performance.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Change Management and Organizational Performance Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-15.178	2.128		-7.131	.000
	Prepare for change	.367	.060	.264	6.110	.000
	Create a vision for change	.215	.046	.183	4.664	.000
	Workplace environment	.596	.049	.519	12.116	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

Table 4. displayed the multiple regression analysis result for change management and organizational performance. It was indicated that Prepare for change which is the first variable has positive effect on organizational performance ($\beta = 0.264$, $P < 0.05$). Create a vision for change which is the second variable has positive effect on organizational performance ($\beta = 0.183$, $P < 0.05$). Similarly, it was reported that Implement change which is the third variable has positive effect on organizational performance ($\beta = 0.084$, $P < 0.05$). It was also indicated that Embed and solidify change which is the fourth variable has positive effect on organizational performance ($\beta = 0.278$, $P < 0.05$).

The general form of the equation to predict $OP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PC + \beta_2 CVC + \beta_3 IC + \beta_4 ESC + \varepsilon$
 $OP = -15.178 + (0.367 \times PC) + (0.215 \times CVC) + (0.110 \times IC) + (0.327 \times ESC)$

Table 5 Fitness of the Model (Analysis of Variance)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	141.243	5	28.249	101.164	.000 ^b
	Residual	59.757	214	.279		
	Total	201.000	219			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Embed and solidify change, Implement change, Create a vision for change, Prepare for change (PC)

Table 5 F-ratio evaluates how well the regression model fits the data. According to the table, organisational performance is strongly predicted by the change management dimensions (F=101.164, p< 0.05). This suggests that the regression model fits the data quite well.

Table 6 Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.838 ^a	.703	.696	.5284

a. Predictors: (Constant), Embed and solidify change, Implement change, Create a vision for change, Prepare for change (PC)

Table .6 presents the degree to which the dimensions of change management explained the variation in organisational performance. The R Square value indicates that change management accounts for 70% (0.696) of the variation in organisational performance. The R Square shows the extent to which variations in the predictor variable can account for variation in the dependent variable.

Hypotheses Testing

The multiple regression analysis was adopted as an analytical technique for testing the hypotheses. The p-values reported in the regression coefficient tables were used for testing the study hypotheses.

The Decision Rule

The null hypothesis will be accepted, and the alternative hypothesis will be rejected if the critical value is determined above the probability level of significance, and vice versa. If the probability value of 0.000 is less than the crucial value of 5% (i.e., 0.000 0.05), there is no need to conclude that the supplied parameter is significantly essential. In this case, it is permissible to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis. When we reject the null hypothesis, we state our results are statistically significant, and vice versa (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

H₀₁: Prepare for change (PC) has no significant positive effect on the organizational performance of the telecommunication industry under study.

The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate was accepted since the p-value critical is at 0.05 (5%) i.e., the level of significance, or the admissible error in estimate, is less than the computed level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) in table 4. This suggests that Delta State's deposit money banks' organisational performance is significantly improved by Prepare for Change (PC).

H₀₂: Creating a vision for change has no significant positive effect on the organisational performance. Telecommunication industry under study.

The computed level of significance, as shown in Table .4, is less than the p-value of 5%, i.e. ($0.000 < 0.05$). This finding suggests that creating a vision for change significantly improves the organisational performance of telecommunication firms in Warri, rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative.

Discussion of Results

The explanation of the study's findings is given below by the data analysis completed in chapter four and the chapter two survey of relevant literature. The characteristics of change management strongly predict organizational performance, as shown by the F-ratio in Table 5 test ($F = 101.164, p < 0.05$). This suggests that the regression model fits the data quite well. Table .6 demonstrates that change management accounts for 70% (0.696) of the variation in organisational performance.

Prepare for change (PC) and Organizational Performance

According to Table 3, Prepare for Change (PC) and organizational success have a positive correlation coefficient (0.585), indicating that preparing for change is an excellent indicator of how well a company manages its reputation. Preparing for change (PC) improves organisational performance, according to Table 4 ($\beta = 0.264, P < 0.05$). The alternate hypothesis was approved since the p-value critical is at 0.05 (5%) i.e., the level of significance, or the allowable error in the estimate, is less than the computed level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) in Table 4. This suggests that Prepare for Change greatly enhances the performance of Delta State's deposit money banks. This is in line with the research conducted by Egbosionu (2020) who found that preparing for change is driven by internal factors such as performance improvement or external factors such as market shifts, by assessing the organization's readiness for change by evaluating the organization's capacity, culture, and the level of support from leadership and employees. Also, this corroborates the findings of Ekechi & Umar (2020), who state that by identifying and analyzing stakeholders: Understand who will be affected by the change and how. This includes employees, customers, suppliers, and other relevant parties. Communicate the need for change, involve key stakeholders in the decision-making process, and address concerns to gain their support.

Create a vision for change and Organizational Performance

According to Table 3, Create a vision for change and organisational success have a positive correlation coefficient (0.361), suggesting that creating a vision for change is an excellent indicator of how well a company manages its reputation. According to Table .4, Creating a vision for change improves organisational performance ($\beta = 0.183, P < 0.05$). According to Table 4, the computed level of significance is less than the 5% p-value, or ($0.000 < 0.05$). The alternative hypothesis, which maintains that creating a vision for change greatly enhances the organisational performance of telecommunication firms in Warri, was accepted because of this study. The results of the study are in line with those of Etikan & Bala (2017) who found a comprehensive plan by outlining the scope, objectives, timelines, and resources required for the change initiative. Identifying risks by anticipating potential challenges developing strategies to mitigate risks and establishing measurable metrics to assess the success of the change (Fadila & Umar, 2021) also, clearly articulate the reasons for the change, its benefits, and how it will be

implemented, by ensuring that employees have the necessary knowledge and skills to adapt to the changes. Training programs may include workshops, seminars, and online resources).

Conclusion

The study concluded that organisational performance in telecommunication firms in Warri is highly impacted by change management telecommunication firms in Warri, preparing for change and creating a vision for change, Organizations should employ the service of internal change managers to work together with such experts employed externally to facilitate growth in performance and smooth change implementation. Managers are advised to anticipate change, especially in the telecommunication industry where changes occur every second.

Recommendations

- ❖ The study recommended that change is a crucial component of success If it is purposefully established, properly implemented, and adapted, change in an organization's strategy can affect how it functions, affecting everything from the organizational structure to employees' everyday activities.
- ❖ A clear vision for change can foster a culture of innovation and adaptability within the organization
- ❖ Preparing for change must be considered as a valuable strategic tool that could enhance smooth business operations.

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